

Investigation of the discharge coefficient in the laminar boundary layer regime of critical flow Venturi nozzles calibrated with different gases including hydrogen

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ABSTRACT

This study represents the first step towards the introduction of critical flow Venturi nozzles into the traceability scheme for gaseous hydrogen and addresses the characterisation of the hydrogen discharge coefficient in the laminar boundary layer regime and the identification of a potential alternative gas for nozzle calibration. The experimental study presented was performed for two nozzles with a throat diameter of 0.175 mm and 0.436 mm. The tests were performed with six different gases, including hydrogen, covering a Reynolds number range from $1.5 \cdot 10^3$ to $6 \cdot 10^4$. The experimental results show that the discharge coefficient depends not only on the Reynolds number but also on the isentropic exponent of the gas. Based on the experimental data, theoretical models taking into account the isentropic exponent and the Prandtl number of the gas were evaluated. The study indicates possibilities to use inert gases instead of hydrogen in calibration processes.

1. Introduction

Hydrogen technologies are gaining momentum because they offer the possibility of decarbonising industrial processes and economic sectors. This in turn requires ensuring metrological traceability of hydrogen flow measurements in the entire distribution chain leading from the hydrogen production facilities to end users. This can be achieved by building suitable primary standards as well as by using appropriate secondary standards for measurements of hydrogen flow rate. Due to already existing infrastructure for flow calibrations with inert gases and high flammability of hydrogen, it is also desirable to use other (conventional) gases instead of hydrogen in calibration processes.

This paper focuses on introducing critical flow Venturi nozzles (CFVNs) into the gaseous hydrogen flow traceability chain. The CFVNs have proven to be very stable and widely used secondary standards for measuring the gas flow rate. The gas flow rate q_m through the nozzle is determined as

$$q_m = C_d q_{m,id} \quad (1)$$

where C_d is the discharge coefficient and $q_{m,id}$ is the ideal mass flow rate.

The ideal mass flow rate is calculated assuming the one-dimensional isentropic flow of ideal gas

$$q_{m,id} = \frac{AC^* p_0}{\sqrt{RT_0/M}} \quad (2)$$

where A is the cross-section at the nozzle throat ($A = \pi d_{th}^2/4$, where d_{th} is the nozzle throat diameter), C^* is the critical flow function, R is the gas constant, M molar mass of the gas and p_0 and T_0 are the stagnation pressure and temperature, respectively.

The geometries and calculation methodology for the flow rate through the nozzle are described in ISO 9300 [1]. It is assumed that the discharge coefficient depends only on the geometry of the nozzle and the Reynolds number, which is defined as:

$$Re = \frac{4q_m}{\pi d_{th} \eta_0} \quad (3)$$

where η_0 is the dynamic viscosity of the gas at stagnation inlet conditions. However, this is only a simplification, as several theoretical models have been developed to characterise the discharge coefficient showing the dependence of the discharge coefficient also on the

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thermodynamic properties of the gases. These models can be divided into those that focus on the non-idealities of the core flow [2,3] and those that discuss viscous effects of the boundary layer [4,5,6,7].

There are only a small number of published studies dealing with hydrogen flow measurements with CFVNs. Tang and Fenn [8] presented an experimental study for Reynolds numbers up to $1 \cdot 10^4$. They also showed that the discharge coefficient can be satisfactorily predicted by their analytical model based on an axisymmetric compressible laminar flow boundary layer under adiabatic conditions, assuming that the viscosity changes linearly with temperature. However, the authors reported relatively large measurement uncertainties of about 2 %. Johnson et al. [9] showed a strong agreement between the values of the discharge coefficient of hydrogen for a toroidal nozzle obtained with their CFD numerical model and the experimental data. Some recent numerical studies [10,11,12] indicate that the real gas effects become substantial for high pressure hydrogen nozzle flows.

In order to introduce CFVNs into the traceability chain for the gaseous hydrogen flow rate, the present study, prepared in the framework of EMPIR MetHyInfra Joint Research Project, addresses the characterisation of the hydrogen discharge coefficient in the laminar boundary layer regime and the identification of a potential alternative gas for the nozzle calibration. The experimental study is based on a comparison of the discharge coefficients of two toroidal nozzles of different sizes with six different gases: dry air, argon, helium, hydrogen, nitrogen and nitrous oxide. The study also investigates the applicability of different theoretical models for predictions of the discharge coefficients for the nozzles when used with different gases.

The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the theoretical approach for modelling the discharge coefficient as a function of nozzle dimensions and gas properties according to Kliegel and Levine [3] and Geropp [6,7]. Two variants of the described approach were used for prediction of discharge coefficients of the tested gases, using the experimental nitrogen data as a reference. Section 3 describes the measuring system and the test procedure used in the experiments. A comparative analysis of the experimentally determined discharge coefficients and the predictions of the theoretical models for the tested gases are presented in Section 4.

2. Discharge coefficient and its theoretical dependencies on dimensions and gas properties

The value of the discharge coefficient is related to the viscous effects in the boundary layer ($C_{d_{visc}}$) and multi-dimensional feature of the inviscid core flow ($C_{d_{inv}}$). Since the coefficients are almost independent of each other, the discharge coefficient can be approximated as [13]:

$$C_d \approx C_{d_{inv}} C_{d_{visc}} \quad (4)$$

The viscous effects of the boundary layer $C_{d_{visc}}$ are related to the displacement thickness δ_1 of the boundary layer, so that

$$C_{d_{visc}} = \left(1 - 2 \frac{\delta_1}{d_{th}}\right)^2 \quad (5)$$

In case of laminar boundary layers, the displacement thickness δ_1 develops proportional with the inverse square root of Reynolds number

$$\delta_1 \sim \frac{1}{\sqrt{Re}} \quad (6)$$

Taking the equations above we get

$$C_d = a \left(1 - \frac{b}{2\sqrt{Re}}\right)^2 = a \left(1 - \frac{b}{\sqrt{Re}} + \frac{b^2}{4Re}\right) \quad (7)$$

where $a = C_{d_{inv}}$ and $b = 4\sqrt{Re} \frac{\delta_1}{d_{th}}$. Considering the parameter a is close to unity and the term $\frac{b^2}{4Re}$ is negligible for higher Reynolds numbers (with $b = 3.412$ and $Re \geq 2 \cdot 10^4$, i.e. $\frac{b^2}{4Re} \leq 1.46 \cdot 10^{-4}$), the C_d can be approximated

by $a - \frac{b}{\sqrt{Re}}$ which is the form of C_d given by the ISO 9300 [1].

According to Kliegel and Levine [3] the coefficient a can be given as a function of isentropic exponent κ and curvature of nozzle contour $R_C = R/d_{th}$ (R is throat wall radius) at the throat¹:

$$C_{d_{inv}} = a(\kappa, R_C) \\ = 1 - \frac{\kappa + 1}{96(2R_C + 1)^2} + \frac{(\kappa + 1)(8\kappa - 27)}{2304(2R_C + 1)^3} - \frac{(\kappa + 1)(754\kappa^2 - 757\kappa + 3633)}{276480(2R_C + 1)^4} \quad (8)$$

The development of the boundary layer or its displacement thickness δ_1 is, in addition to the Reynolds number, also a function of the acceleration of the core flow. The acceleration is hereby for nozzles with toroidal shapes a function of the throat curvature R_C . In several publications, e.g. [4,6,7], the general relationship is documented as:

$$b = \frac{4\delta_1}{d_{th}} \sqrt{Re} = G R_C^{0.25} \quad (9)$$

The factor G represents the dependence of the mass flow defect on the velocity and density distribution within the boundary layer and is therefore a function of the isentropic exponent κ , Prandtl number Pr and the temperature difference ΔT_W between the gas and the nozzle body at the nozzle wall $G = G(\kappa, Pr, \Delta T_W)$. In 1971, Geropp [6] introduced a specific shape of nozzle that is not identical to a toroidal nozzle, but is quite similar to it near the throat. The construction of this shape is based on the so-called shape factor m . At the throat m is only function of the throat curvature and the isentropic exponent $m^2 = \frac{2}{R_C} \left(\frac{2}{\kappa+1}\right)^{\frac{1-\kappa}{\kappa+1}}$. Assuming adiabatic walls and a Prandtl number of the gas $Pr = 1$ and using similarity transformations, the Navier-Stokes-equation for the laminar boundary layer can be solved analytically. The solution gives an expression for the displacement thickness along the nozzle axis in dependency of the curvature radius, isentropic exponent as well as Reynolds number and therefore also the C_d value. Independently, Tang [8] used a similar approach in his work. In 1987, Geropp [7] extended his solution to satisfy also non-adiabatic walls and gases with $Pr \neq 1$. The outcome is quite similar and provides finally the factor $G = G(\kappa, Pr, \Delta T_W)$ depending also on Prandtl number Pr and wall temperature difference ΔT_W . With $Pr = 1$ and $\Delta T_W = 0$, this solution is identical to the previous.

The actual formula given in [7] for the displacement thickness is very complex. However, in the present work there is no specific information about the temperature of the nozzle wall, only that the stagnation temperature of the gas and the ambient temperature were almost identical and close to 22 °C (laboratory conditions). Thus, if we assume $\Delta T_W = 0$ due to the lack of information², we can establish a linear approximation based on tabulated values for $G = G(\kappa, Pr, \Delta T_W = 0)$ and varying $1.2 \leq \kappa \leq 1.7$ as well as $0.6 \leq Pr \leq 1$ to cover a practical range:

$$G(\kappa, Pr) = 2.9615[1 + 0.2071(\kappa - 1.4) + 0.1243(Pr - 1)] \quad (10)$$

For air ($\kappa = 1.41$, $Pr = 0.72$) and $R_C = 2$, the factor G equals 2.865 and the coefficients $a = 0.9988$ and $b = 3.407$, which is in good agreement with ISO 9300 values for toroidal nozzles ($a_{ISO} = 0.9986$ and $b_{ISO} = 3.412$).

3. Test setup and test procedure

The measurements were carried out for two toroidal CFVNs with two different throat diameters, both part of a five-nozzle array (Tetracat)

¹ The Kliegel-Levine calculation [3] is preferred because of its better approximation compared to the more popular solution of Hall [2], especially for small R_C .

² The experiences in the past showed that the solution of [7] underestimated the impact of heat transfer through the nozzle wall. The dependency on ΔT_W is according to [14] about 5 times higher.

with an inlet conduit diameter of $D = 10$ mm:

- nozzle 1; $d_{th,1} = 0.175$ mm,
- nozzle 2; $d_{th,2} = 0.436$ mm,

where the given diameters are the values provided by the manufacturer. The test setup is shown schematically in Fig. 1. High pressure cylinders (50 L) were used as the gas source. The pressure regulator (stage 1) was connected to the outlet of the gas cylinder and set to about 1 MPa. To achieve suitable temperature stabilisation, the gas was passed through a coil before reaching the pressure regulator (Bronkhorst, EL-PRESS P-502C), which was used to set the absolute inlet pressure of the CFVNs in the range between 200 kPa and 700 kPa. The pressure (Mensor, CGP2500 & CPR2550, $U(k=2) = 0.02\%$ MV or 80 Pa) and temperature (Tetratec & PicoTechnology; 535 T 161 & PT-104, $U(k=2) = 0.2\%$ °C) of the gas were measured at the inlet manifold of the CFVNs. The piston prover (Sierra Instruments (Bios), Cal = Trak SL-800 & SL-800-44, $U(k=2) = 0.15\%$), which was used as a flow standard, was connected to the outlet of the CFVNs. All components were connected to the PC using the control programme realised in the LabVIEW programming environment. The programme enabled the control of the pressure at the input of the CFVNs and the storage of all necessary data for further processing.

Special precautions were taken for working with hydrogen. First, before working with hydrogen, the tightness of all connections was tested with helium using a helium sniffer. During the hydrogen flow measurements, part of the measuring system (CFVNs, the pressure regulator and the piston prover) was placed under the fume hood as shown in Fig. 2. With the help of a suitable ventilation system, the gas under the fume hood was discharged to the outside environment.

The measurements for each CFVN were carried out at six measurement points: at nominal inlet pressures p_1 equal to (200, 300, 400, 500, 600, 700) kPa. Three repetitions were carried out at each measuring point. The reference mass flow rate was determined as the mean of ten consecutive readings of the piston prover. The results at each measurement point consist of three main parameters: the reference mass flow rate ($q_{m,ref}$), the pressure (p_1) and the temperature (T_1) at the inlet of the CFVN. The inlet temperature during the measurements was (22 ± 1) °C.

Fig. 1. Scheme of the test setup.

The calibration of the nozzles was carried out with six different gases (the purity of each gas is shown in parentheses):

- dry air,
- Ar - argon (99.999 %),
- He - helium (99.9996 %),
- H₂ - hydrogen (99.9995 %),
- N₂ - nitrogen (99.999 %),
- N₂O - nitrous oxide (99.5 %).

All properties of the gases were defined using REFPROP v9.0 database [15]. Table 1 shows gas properties for all gases at average test conditions: absolute pressure 450 kPa and temperature 22 °C.

4. Results

The experimentally determined values of the discharge coefficients for both nozzles and all gases considered are shown in Fig. 3 as a function of $Re^{0.5}$. The C_d values were calculated using eq. (1) and (2) for the throat diameters given by the manufacturer of the nozzles (see Section 3) and since $d_{th}/D < 0.16$ for both nozzles, the values for inlet pressure (p_1) and temperature (T_1) were used instead of stagnation pressure (p_0) and temperature (T_0) [1]. The expanded uncertainty of the calculated discharge coefficient based on the uncertainties of the reference mass flow rate, inlet pressure and temperature (given in Section 3) is about $U(C_d) = 0.17\%$. However, the measurement uncertainty does not include components related to the temperature stabilisation of the nozzle, so it could be underestimated.

The results in Fig. 3 show that the Reynolds numbers for the different gases do not completely overlap in range of tested inlet pressures. Almost overlapping ranges of Reynolds numbers are observed for air, nitrogen and argon for both nozzles; from about $4 \cdot 10^3$ to $1.5 \cdot 10^4$ for nozzle 1. The highest Re numbers are observed for nitrous oxide (up to about $2.3 \cdot 10^4$ for nozzle 1), while the lowest values are found for helium (about $1.4 \cdot 10^3$ for nozzle 1). For all gases, there is almost no common overlap of Reynolds numbers in the range of inlet pressures tested, so that the discharge coefficients obtained can be compared directly. Note that the mentioned values of the Reynolds numbers for nozzle 2 are about 2.5 times larger.

For both nozzles, similar trends are observed in the discharge coefficients for a given gas. The C_d values of air and nitrogen for both nozzles are almost identical and agree very well with those of hydrogen in the overlap region. The results also show that the discharge coefficients for argon and helium are about 0.5 % lower in the overlap region of Reynolds numbers compared to nitrogen (or air or hydrogen), while they are about 1 % higher for nitrous oxide. Considering the reported uncertainties for C_d and the observed repeatability, the observed differences can be considered significant. The differences in C_d for helium and argon also correlate with some previous experimental data [8,16,17].

Taking the experimental data of nitrogen as a reference, we will next consider the deviations of the theoretical predictions for other gases compared to nitrogen. In this way, we can estimate how consistently the nitrogen calibration result can be applied to other gases (within the limits and assumptions of each model studied). Three theoretical modelling approaches were considered (in all cases C_d is defined according to eq.(7)):

- Model A: coefficients a and b are independent of the type of the gas. Values of coefficients a and b , which were obtained by fitting nitrogen data using ordinary least square algorithm were used also for other gases;
- Model B: coefficients a and b are based on $G(\kappa_{N_2}, Pr_{N_2})$. The values of d_{th} and Re_c are calculated for nitrogen data and later used to calculate the coefficients a and b for other gases based on $G(\kappa_{othGas}, Pr_{othGas})$. This model assumes $Pr = 1$. Detailed explanation on calculation of d_{th}

Fig. 2. Measuring system with the fume hood.

Table 1

Gas properties at average test conditions: absolute pressure 450 kPa and temperature 22 °C.

Gas	ρ kg/m ³	η Pa s	C^* /	κ /	Pr /	M /
air	5.320	18.354	0.686	1.408	0.711	28.965
Ar	7.347	22.495	0.728	1.680	0.668	39.948
H ₂	0.369	8.862	0.686	1.406	0.690	2.016
He	0.732	19.722	0.726	1.666	0.663	4.003
N ₂	5.142	17.713	0.686	1.408	0.721	28.013
N ₂ O	8.281	14.797	0.672	1.304	0.729	44.013

and R_c and determination of coefficients a and b is given in Appendix A;

- Model C: The same as the model B, but with actual value of Pr .

The values of κ and Pr considered in the models B and C were determined at mean pressure of 450 kPa and inlet temperature $T_1 = 22$ °C, see Table 1. The maximum deviations of κ and Pr from the values in Table 1 due to the temperature variations during the tests are smaller than 0.17 % and 0.11 %, respectively, which was proven not to have any notable influence on calculated coefficients a and b .

The estimated values of all parameters for all three models and for both nozzles can be found in Table 2. The last line of the table (Δd_{th}) shows the difference between the throat diameter given by the manufacturer and the calculated diameter. For the model B, the deviations are about 0.28 μm for nozzle 1 and -0.13 μm for nozzle 2. For the model C, the deviation remains the same for the smaller nozzle, while it changes to -0.08 μm for the larger nozzle. Considering that the typical uncertainty of coordinate machine measurements is about 0.5 μm – 1 μm [18,19], these results show very good agreement with the throat diameters specified by the manufacturer. The comparison of the coefficients a and b between the models B and C also shows minimal differences for both nozzles, while the calculated throat curvature R_c is slightly different. The values of coefficients a and b for both nozzles and different gases calculated according to the models B and C are stated in Tables 3 and 4.

To compare the capability of different theoretical models to predict the discharge coefficient or the mass flow rate of different gases through

Fig. 3. Experimentally determined C_d values for different gases – a) nozzle 1 and b) nozzle 2; estimated expanded uncertainties of C_d values equal 0.17 %.

the nozzle by taking nitrogen as a reference gas, we defined a relative deviation ε for each gas as:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{q_m^{(model)}}{q_{m,ref}} - 1 = \frac{C_d^{(model)}}{C_d} - 1 \quad (11)$$

where $q_m^{(model)}$ and $C_d^{(model)}$ represent the mass flow rate and the value of the discharge coefficient, respectively, both determined by the selected modelling approaches (using one of the discussed models) for a specific gas according to eq. (7) and the coefficients a , b and d_{th} given in Tables 2 to 4. The value of C_d in the above equation is the discharge coefficient

Table 2

Calculated parameters according to the three modelling approaches of C_d for both nozzles considering a nitrogen as the reference gas.

	Nozzle 1			Nozzle 2		
	Model A	Model B	Model C	Model A	Model B	Model C
a	0.9967	0.9999	0.9999	0.9996	0.9990	0.9992
b	4.844	4.847	4.847	3.625	3.625	3.625
G	–	2.966	2.863	–	2.966	2.863
R_c	–	7.13	8.21	–	2.23	2.57
d_{th} [mm]	0.175	0.17472	0.17472	0.436	0.43613	0.43608
Δd_{th} [μ m]	–	0.28	0.28	–	–0.13	–0.08

Table 3

Coefficients a and b for both nozzles according to the model B.

	Nozzle 1		Nozzle 2	
	a	b	a	b
Air	0.9999	4.848	0.9990	3.626
Ar	0.9999	5.120	0.9989	3.829
H ₂	0.9999	4.846	0.9990	3.624
He	0.9999	5.106	0.9989	3.819
N ₂	0.9999	4.847	0.9990	3.625
N ₂ O	0.9999	4.743	0.9991	3.547

Table 4

Coefficients a and b for both nozzles according to the model C.

	Nozzle 1		Nozzle 2	
	a	b	a	b
Air	0.9999	4.841	0.9992	3.621
Ar	0.9999	5.097	0.9992	3.812
H ₂	0.9999	4.827	0.9992	3.610
He	0.9999	5.080	0.9992	3.799
N ₂	0.9999	4.847	0.9992	3.625
N ₂ O	0.9999	4.744	0.9993	3.548

determined upon the experimental data for particular gas and considering d_{th} corresponding to the selected model.

For the model A, the estimated deviations of both nozzles are shown in Fig. 4. The trends of the specific gases are more or less continuous with Reynolds number, except for C_d of nitrous oxide. As already noted before, the predictions for nitrogen, air and also hydrogen agree well even with constant values of the coefficients a and b . The deviations are smaller than 0.2 % in the entire range (except for hydrogen at the lowest Reynolds number), which corresponds approximately to the estimated U (C_d). The deviations for argon and helium, the two monatomic gases, are positive; they range from about 0.3 % to almost 1 %, with the highest observed values at the lowest Reynolds number, which is significant

Fig. 4. Relative deviations for the model A for both nozzles (nozzle 1 – hollow markers, nozzle 2 – filled markers); estimated expanded uncertainties of presented data equal 0.17 %.

with respect to $U(C_d)$. The higher absolute values of the deviations at the smallest Reynolds numbers may also be caused in part by the fact that nitrogen (or air) does not overlap with hydrogen and helium, or they may also be caused by improper stabilisation of the temperature in the tests. On the other hand, the data for nitrous oxide show larger deviations, ranging from -0.5 % and even up to -1.5 %. The results make it clear that models that use constant values for the coefficients a and b (analogous to the ISO 9300 approach) cannot be successfully applied for all gases used in the study.

Based on the results shown in Figs. 3 and 4, we can identify three groups of gases which share similar behaviour: (i) helium and argon, (ii) air, nitrogen and hydrogen and (iii) nitrous oxide. As given in Table 1 the gases belonging to a specific group can be characterised by a similar value of the isentropic exponent; for helium and argon around 1.67, for air, nitrogen and hydrogen about 1.41 and for nitrous oxide its value is about 1.30. Considering this fact, it can be expected that the deviation for argon, helium and nitrous oxide for the models B and C, which take into account the dependency of the coefficient a and b on the type of the gas, will be smaller.

Figs. 5 and 6 show relative deviations of both nozzles according to the models B and C. Both models show very similar results regardless of the observed gas. Compared to the model A they predict significantly smaller deviations for helium and argon, but some differences in general not larger than 0.3 % remain. On the other hand, compared to the model A deviations of the models B and C for nitrous oxide do not change much. This shows that behaviour of the nitrous oxide is not primarily influenced by the isentropic exponent, but other intra-molecular effects; see e.g., [16,20,21] for vibrational relaxation effects in CO₂ and SF₆. Similar predictions of the models B and C for all gases indicate that taking into account the actual value of Pr for the tested toroidal nozzles and the gases under consideration does not produce any notable difference. This finding confirms the predictions from Ref. [9], which was based on the solutions of the computational model for adiabatic nozzle.

Very close resemblance to the deviations of the models B and C were already seen in Ref. [22], where these experimental data were compared to the predictions of combined Hall-Geropp model presented by Ishibashi and Takamoto [23]. Also, Tang and Fenn [8] showed that C_d for nitrogen, hydrogen, argon and helium coincide relatively well with their theoretical model at Re greater than $1 \cdot 10^3$, which also exhibits dependence of C_d on κ .

5. Conclusion

We have presented a comprehensive experimental study on the behaviour of CFVNs with hydrogen in the laminar boundary layer regime including a direct comparison with some other gases. The discharge coefficients were experimentally determined for two different toroidal CFVNs with throat diameters of 0.175 mm and 0.436 mm with six different gases: air, argon, helium, hydrogen, nitrogen and nitrous

Fig. 5. Relative deviations for the model B for both nozzles (nozzle 1 – hollow markers, nozzle 2 – filled markers); estimated expanded uncertainties of presented data equal 0.17 %.

Fig. 6. Relative deviations for the model C for both nozzles (nozzle 1 – hollow markers, nozzle 2 – filled markers); estimated expanded uncertainties of presented data equal 0.17 %.

oxide. The measurements for each CFVN were carried out at the absolute inlet pressures from 200 kPa to 700 kPa, which cover the range of Reynolds numbers from about $1.5 \cdot 10^3$ to $6 \cdot 10^4$. The expanded uncertainty of the estimated discharge coefficients for all gases was about 0.17 %.

The experimental results show that the discharge coefficient depends not only on the Reynolds number but also on the isentropic exponent of the gas. The discharge coefficients of air, nitrogen and hydrogen, which all have approximately the same value of isentropic exponent, agree within 0.2 %, which is of the same order of magnitude as their expanded uncertainty. For helium and argon, the monatomic noble gases with higher isentropic coefficients, the discharge coefficients were about (0.6 ± 0.3) % smaller than those of nitrogen with larger differences observed at lower Reynolds numbers. For nitrous oxide, on the other hand, which has the lowest isentropic exponent among the gases tested, the discharge coefficient increased by (1.0 ± 0.5) %. In addition, it has been shown for all gases that the discharge coefficients are continuous with the Reynolds number, except for nitrous oxide, whose values also depend on the nozzle size.

The experimental data were also used to evaluate how consistently the nitrogen calibration result can be applied to other gases by using two theoretical models for the discharge coefficient, termed as the model B and C. Both models are based on the Kliegel-Levine solution [3] for the core flow and the Geropp treatment of the boundary layer. In the model B, the boundary layer effects are determined assuming that the Prandtl number is equal to one and the wall is adiabatic [6], while the model C considers the actual Prandtl number for a given gas [7]. The model C can generally also take into account the wall temperature difference ΔT_w between the gas and the nozzle wall (due to lack of data $\Delta T_w = 0$ in the present analysis). The discharge coefficient for helium and argon can be predicted well with both models, the deviation between the predicted and the actual discharge coefficients is mostly within 0.3 %, which is about twice better than in the earlier uncorrected case. However, the models are not able to explain the observed behaviour of nitrous oxide, probably due to its significant intra-molecular relaxation effects. Similar predictions of the models B and C indicate that taking into account the actual Prandtl number is not significant for the nozzles and the gases considered, which proves the prediction by Johnson et al. [9] which was

achieved using the computational model. Nevertheless, the use of the model C is recommended, especially when it can be supported by the wall temperature difference data.

The results show that CFVNs used with hydrogen in the tested range of Reynolds numbers in the laminar boundary layer regime can potentially be calibrated with alternative gases. The first choice would probably be air or nitrogen, whose values of discharge coefficients match those of hydrogen quite well. By ensuring a comparable range of Reynolds numbers in the air or nitrogen calibration with that corresponding to hydrogen flow, the calibration results can be directly applied to hydrogen as well, without having to consider additional corrections. Another possibility is to use another alternative gas (e.g. helium) in the calibration, for which the comparable Reynolds number range can be achieved more easily, and then use the theoretical models to predict the behaviour of the CFVN with hydrogen. Due to the inaccuracy of the theoretical models presented, this will increase the final uncertainty of the hydrogen flow rate measurements.

Since the extrapolation of obtained results to higher Reynolds numbers (turbulent boundary layer) is not straightforward an investigation of the behaviour of nozzles at higher flow rates is planned within the MetHyInfra project. First, a comparison of selected toroidal and cylindrical nozzles of different roughness will be carried out with inert gases (air, nitrogen, helium) at higher flow rates using existing calibration facilities. Finally, these nozzles will be tested with hydrogen using a primary standard developed within the project.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Gregor Bobovnik: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Visualization. **Bodo Mickan:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Writing – original draft. **Peter Sambol:** Investigation, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Rémy Maury:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Jože Kutin:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Appendix A.: Empirical determination of the nozzle throat diameter d_{th} and throat curvature R_C (using ordinary least squares method)

Based on the definition of the discharge coefficient in eqs. (1) and (7) and introducing the critical mass flow density $\psi_{id} = C^* \frac{p_0}{\sqrt{RT_0/M}}$, the discharge coefficient C_d can be written as:

$$C_d = \frac{4q_m}{\pi d_{th}^2 \psi_{id}} = a \left(1 - \frac{b}{\sqrt{Re}} + \frac{b^2}{4Re} \right) \quad (A1)$$

In the present work, the Reynolds numbers go down to $Re \approx 1,500$, so that the term $\frac{b^2}{4Re}$ is of the order of 0.002, which is larger than the uncertainty

of the reference mass flow rate. Thus, for such small Reynolds numbers, it is better to keep the full relation to avoid unnecessary systematic deviations due to linear approximation. However, the quadratic form of the full equation for C_d is inconvenient if we want to determine the parameters using ordinary least squares (OLS) method. Fortunately, this can be solved by a suitable transformation, which makes it possible to additionally determine the throat diameter d_{th} and throat curvature R_C as well. Eq. (A1) can be transformed as follows:

$$\frac{4}{\pi} \frac{q_m}{\psi_{id}} = a d_{th}^2 \left(1 - \frac{b}{2\sqrt{Re}}\right)^2 \quad (A2)$$

and by taking the square root operation as:

$$\frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sqrt{\frac{q_m}{\psi_{id}}} = \sqrt{a} d_{th} \left(1 - \frac{b}{2\sqrt{Re}}\right) = \sqrt{a} d_{th} - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\sqrt{a} d_{th} b}{\sqrt{Re}} \quad (A3)$$

Introducing the relation for Reynolds number from eq. (3) we get

$$\frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sqrt{\frac{q_m}{\psi_{id}}} = (\sqrt{a} d_{th}) - (\sqrt{a} d_{th})^{1.5} \frac{b}{a^{0.25}} \sqrt{\frac{\eta_0}{q_m}} \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{4} \quad (A4)$$

The latter formula is of linear structure:

$$y = p_1 + p_2 x \quad (A5)$$

where x , y , p_1 and p_2 are given as

$$y = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sqrt{\frac{q_m}{\psi_{id}}}; \quad x = -\frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{4} \sqrt{\frac{\eta_0}{q_m}}; \quad p_1 = \sqrt{a} d_{th}; \quad p_2 = \frac{b}{a^{0.25}} p_1^{1.5} \quad (A6)$$

The coefficients p_1 and p_2 can be determined by least square tools and thus d_{th} and b can be calculated as follows:

$$d_{th} = \frac{p_1}{\sqrt{a}}; \quad b = a^{0.25} \frac{p_2}{p_1^{1.5}} \quad (A7)$$

There is a need of a short iteration (three steps are sufficient) starting with $a = 1$ to get the final values of a , b , d_{th} and R_C (using also relations in eqs. (8) and (9)).

The application of the least square tools gives the uncertainties of the parameter p_1 and p_2 . In case of OLS, the outcome is straight forward and can be transformed into the uncertainties of the related coefficients of a , b , d_{th} and R_C according to conventional propagation of uncertainty using the partial differentials $\partial/\partial p_i$. If the full uncertainty analysis shall be applied using the uncertainties of all input values including their correlations, then an extended total least square calculation is needed (see for example [24]).

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